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The history of the development of the clothing service (in the case of Russia)

Abstract: this article describes the genesis of the history of the development of the clothing service. In addition, the place and role of the clothing service, as well as its tasks, were analyzed. The structure of the clothing service is highlighted.

Key words: clothing, supply, mission, structure, history, equipment, army, military personnel, military supply.

From 1699 all newly formed regular regiments were to receive all clothing, equipment, and other allowances from the treasury in time of peace and war. Meeting the needs of the army under this new order of supply was beyond the authority of rank and other commands, and necessitated the establishment of independent departments to take over all the concerns of the economy of the troops. The Special Order was established by royal decree of February 18, 1700. The "Special Order" was tasked with providing the regiments with clothing, equipment, and wages. The publication of states, tables and rules began two years after the Poltava victory. Prior to the issuance of administrative regulations, economic bodies followed private orders or acted "as usual" in their actions. In 1708, a single office was established for the purchase of clothing, linen, shoes, and equipment. Subsequently, there were three such offices, namely: the Infantry Uniform Office, the Cavalry Uniform Office, and the Izhora Uniform Office. With the new administrative structure of the Russian state based on the decree of Peter the Great on December 18, 1708, according to which the entire territory of Russia was divided into 8 regions and 39 regions under the control of governors. governors, the importance of military order, as well as central institutions temporarily fell. After this reform, it was determined that all state duties and expenses would be transferred to the provincial treasury, so that all the needs of the army could be met without worrying about the government, that is, from the full-fledged provinces. troops are decentralized. In 1711, funds for the maintenance of all regiments were allocated to the provinces, and special commissioners were appointed from them to each separate division, who had to solve all issues of providing the regiments with clothing and ammunition, wages and food. The purchasing part also went to the regions. They were sent the necessary samples for instructions on how to make uniforms and clothes. The abnormality of this system of providing for the army was soon discovered, and from 1713 it was ordered that not only uniforms, but all clothing items be remade in the uniform offices, where the governors were required by law to send money. count. The abnormality of this system of providing for the army was soon discovered, and from 1713 it was ordered that not only uniforms, but all clothing items be remade in the uniform offices, where the governors were required by law to send money. count. Instead of divisional commissions, warehouses were formed, which were not associated with any combat unit of the troops, but with a well-known local region. Local depots were established in St. Petersburg, Riga, Smolensk, Kiev, Kherson, Moscow, and Kazan to directly supply the troops. Depot included the following members: commissary commission; separate commission agents and titles for some points distant from the depot; all commissary institutions in the area.

Each depot also consists of an "availability" and a "workshop", and each additionally has: a treasury department, levels for various tasks, and parcels for preparing items and receiving them. queues for delivery consisted of groups of convoy transport. with things. The clothing allowance was organized according to the approved deadlines and was implemented according to the mixed system. The troops received some items ready-made, while other military units were given money or supplies. Military units were mainly supplied with ready-made goods: ammunition and equipment, saddles and horse equipment, hats without tools, cloth and linen,

leggings and leather goods. Troops were often paid for other things. In some cases, as an exception, with the consent of the commissary departments, the troops could receive everything ready or with all the money.

In 1812, the Military Ministry was established instead of the Military College. In the administration of the Central Commissariat, expeditions received the name of departments. An Army General Field Headquarters was established to manage the Army's economy, which included the Army Quartermaster's Department and the Field Commissary's Department.

The Field Commissariat Department was headed by the Chief Kriegs Commissar and consisted of commissariat commissions under the office, troops, and each separate corps. The office is divided into three sections and a special computer desk. The first division was responsible for the provision of the army and hospitals, the second division distributed supplies and looked after the reserves located within the state. The third department was in charge of hospitals. A special calculation table that deals with reports and accounting.

The left commissar commission consisted of "presence" and "cabinet". "This" includes: the manager of the commission and three members. The office is divided into six desks. Both tables were under the special control of one of the "current" members. The leadership of the commissariat commissions was entrusted to the following: those located under the troops - lieutenants of the chief commissariat, and commissions under separate corps - chief commissariat masters. Such military-economic management lasted until the 60s of that century.

The main disadvantage of this device was its excessive centralization. The concentration of administrative power in the central apparatus deprived the administrative bodies of their independence and limited them to small controls. And also, the commissary department, on the one hand, was responsible for receiving, storing and issuing various things, and on the other hand, for administrative orders. The Commissariat Commission managed the preparation of things and at the same time participated in their reception and delivery to the troops.

During the military reform of Milyutin, three military districts were created, in which, among other administrative bodies, local economic departments were established. In 1864, the General Quarters Department was formed from the Commissary and Supply Departments, which underwent various minor changes until the revolution of 1917. In 1867, a Technical Committee was established within the Directorate of General Quarters, which was transformed from the commission for the introduction of technical improvements in the commissariat and supply units, which had existed since 1863. Since then, the wide use of technology in the production, reception and storage of various commissary items has begun. It should be noted that the emperor was a member of the technical committee.

With the formation of the Red Army, a new stage in the development of the uniform service began. In 1917, the Military Revolutionary Committee (MRC) was formed in Petrograd and was entrusted with the functions of organizing material and other types of material and technical support. An Army Economic Committee (Arkhozkom) was created to manage military-economic activities, which in June 1918 was renamed the General Military-Economic Directorate of the Red Army. Military economic departments were also established in military districts (OVHU) and fronts (VHU front).

Order No. 322 of the Supreme Soviet of January 31, 1922 introduced uniform uniforms and insignia for the units of the Red Army for the first time. The direct supply of troops with clothes was entrusted to the district supply authorities.

By the decision of the Council of People's Commissars No. 39 of August 9, 1935, the Department of Military Economy was divided into two: Department of Clothing and Cargo

Supply and Department of Food Supply. In August 1935, by order of the NPO, categories of clothing and footwear repair were established (small, medium, capital repair and restoration).

According to the order of the NPO of February 19, 1938, the functions of the bathroom and laundry services of the Red Army were transferred to the Military Sanitary Department of the Red Army. Starting from March 1, 1940, a number of organizational measures were implemented based on the experience of combat operations in the Red Army. The Red Army Cargo Supply Department was reorganized into two independent departments in the center and district: the Red Army Cargo Supply Department and the Red Army Cargo Supply Department.

Four departments were established in the center: supply of clothing, supply of transportation, supply of food and housing fund.

On March 1, 1940, two independent departments were created from the Red Army's Department of Packing and Clothing Supply: the Department of Clothing Supply of the Red Army and the Department of Packing and Economic Supplies.

There is no set period of time for wearing active duty military uniforms during wartime. Things were changed because they were actually obsolete and completely unfit for further use.

At the beginning of the war, the Clothing Supply Department managed the bathing and laundry services for the troops. From September 1941 and throughout the war, the General Military Sanitary Department managed bath and laundry services for Red Army troops.

At the beginning of 1942, the supply of clothing to the Red Army was particularly stressful. In the east, the evacuated textile, tailoring and leather-shoe factories were not yet operational, and the existing factories, factories, and workshops still lacked raw materials, electricity, fuel, and labor.

The release of the clothing property of the Red Army began to be carried out according to monthly and quarterly plans - orders approved by the State Defense Committee at the suggestion of the People's Commissariat of Defense. Delivery of clothing to the fronts and military districts was carried out according to the monthly limits approved by the State Defense Committee for each front and military district.

In April 1946, in connection with the establishment of the Ministry of the Armed Forces of the USSR, the Department of Uniform Supply of the State Administration of the Air Force was renamed the Department of Uniform Supply of the State Administration of the Armed Forces. The clothing service in the Great Patriotic War successfully fulfilled the tasks of providing the front with all the necessary things. In connection with the establishment of the Ministry of War in March 1950, the directorate was renamed the Department of Clothing and Cargo Supply of the Ministry of War. In December 1950, the Technical Committee became part of the Department of Clothing and Cargo Supply of the State Department of the Ministry of War.

In connection with the establishment of the Ministry of Defense of the USSR in March 1953, the directorate was recognized as the Department of Clothing and Cargo Supply of the State Institution of the Moscow Region. From June 1953, the directorate was renamed the Department of Clothing and Cargo Supply of the Ministry of Defense. In March 1954, the Department of Clothing and Cargo Supply of the State Military District of the Moscow Region took over the maintenance, accounting and provision of soft equipment and property to units and institutions from the Military Medical Department of the Moscow Region. bath and laundry services to them troops.

In May 1955, the position of chief quartermaster of the Ministry of Defense and its staff was abolished. The Department of Clothing and Convoy Supply of the GI MO was renamed the Department of Clothing and Household Supplies of the Ministry of Defense of the USSR,

subordinated to the head of material and technical support of the Ministry of Defense of the USSR, and from December 1959 - Defense of the USSR deputy minister - head of the department of material and technical support of the Ministry of Defense of the USSR.

Departments of clothing and household goods were established in the military districts under the command of the deputy commander of the district troops for rear services.

From June 1958, during the reorganization, the Department of Supply of Uniforms of the Ministry of Defense of the USSR was established. Corresponding changes have also taken place in the organization of clothing supply departments (troops, fleet groups) of military districts. This name lasted until 1978.

In July 1961, troop bathing and laundry services were transferred from the Department of Defense's Military Medical Office to the Department of Defense's Clothing Supply Department and the Department of Defense's Central Military District Bath and Laundry Department. created.

Since November 1978, the directorate was renamed the Central Material and Technical Directorate of the Ministry of Defense and was transferred to the new headquarters No. 1/27, which consisted of a command, a scientific and technical committee, six departments, a secret department and a directorate. administrative and economic part.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that the clothing service is the main basis of military supply and has a long historical development. Technical means of clothing service means washing, dry cleaning and repair of clothes, washing of employees, repair and maintenance of technical equipment of clothing service, mobile household service complexes, bathroom-laundry disinfection trains, as well as technological means are understood. auxiliary equipment of field laundries, baths, dry cleaning and repair workshops, materials and spare parts for specified technical tools and equipment.

Clothing property includes military uniforms, badges, bedclothes, sheets and blankets, special and sanitary equipment, tents, tarpaulins, soft containers, sports and mountaineering equipment, fabrics and materials for the production of clothing items, and consumables.

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